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SYMPOSIUM

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

**Deliverable D5.2
Symposium**

WP5. Management

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1. Executive summary

This document, D5.2 Symposium Report, is a deliverable of the SUNRISE CSA, which is funded by the European Union's H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 816336.

On February 3rd – 7th, 2020, a series of meetings were organized in Brussels by the SUNRISE consortium, partly in collaboration with Energy-X and the Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU. The week started on February 3rd – 4th with a closed consortium meeting at EERA to finalize the work on the SUNRISE deliverables. On February 5th – 6th, the formal kick-off of SUNERGY took place, the follow-up initiative of the CSAs SUNRISE and Energy-X. At this event over 100 stakeholders of both CSAs gathered for a series of public sessions on February 5th and 6th following a high-level lunch event at the European Parliament on February 5th and ending February 6th noon. February 6th pm and 7th am were spent on public SUNRISE meetings at EERA to collect input for the SUNRISE blueprint, deliverable D1.3.

During the sessions on February 3rd – 4th, the SUNRISE deliverables were reviewed by the consortium as well as the planning of remaining efforts needed to conclude pending deliverables. The discussion was documented and the outcome is presented in this document. The public SUNRISE sessions on February 6th pm and 7th am were used to discuss the programming of future consortia and investment scenarios to realize (parts of) the SUNRISE roadmap. This discussion is also presented in this document.

During the public kick-off meetings on February 5th – 6th, the CSAs SUNRISE and ENERGY-X presented their achievements throughout the past year, and proposed their joint vision on providing sustainable and competitive alternatives to fossil fuels by 2050. Keynote speakers like Peter Dröll (Director Prosperity, Directorate General Research & Innovation) highlighted the strong support of the European institutions towards R&I to achieve the ambitions of the European Green Deal. The session on February 6th am was focused on upcoming funding opportunities and recently awarded projects relevant for SUNERGY.

The public meetings brought together a broad representation of academia, policy, and industrial actors together with NGOs, consumer associations, citizens, students, and press correspondents to mobilize the critical mass needed to implement the future large-scale research initiative SUNERGY.

2. Agenda of the meetings

A. SUNRISE Final Consortium Meetings

Session 1: Deliverables

Monday, 3 February 2020

13:30 – 13:45 Opening words by **Huib de Groot** (LU, SUNRISE CSA coordinator).

13:45 – 15:45 **Deliverables WP 1 Strategy and structuring**

D1.1 Consolidated vision (Nicola Armaroli, CNR)

D1.2 Roadmap (Hervé Bercegol, CEA)

D1.3 Blueprint (Ann Magnuson, UU)

Revision, integration (all)

15:45 – 16:00 *Coffee break*

16:00 – 17:00 **WP 2: Innovation and Exploitation (I)**

D2.1 Innovation process (Arne Roth, Fraunhofer)

D2.2 Innovation structure (Peter Ellis, Johnson Matthey)

17:00 **End of Day 1**

Tuesday, 4 February 2020

9:00 – 10:45 **WP 2: Innovation and Exploitation (II)**

D2.3 Innovation and exploitation plan (Max Fleischer, Siemens)

Revision, integration (all)

10:45 – 11:00 *Coffee break*

11:00 – 12:00 **WP 3: Dissemination, Communication and Education**

D3.1 Dissemination Plan

D3.2 Website & App

D3.3 Resources

D3.4 Data Management Plan

Revision, integration (all)

12:00 – 13:00 *Lunch*

13:00 – 14:00 **D4.1 Governance Plan (Frédéric Chandezon, CEA)**

Discussion next steps, all

14:00 – 14:15 *Coffee break*

14:15 – 17:00 D4.2 Terms of Reference (Max Fleischer, Siemens)

Revision, integration with D1.3 Blueprint (all)

17:00 End of the meeting

Session 2: Programming future consortia

Thursday, 6 February 2020 PM, 13.00 - 17.00

Blueprint - 100% scenario.

Aim: Collect input from SUNRISE consortium members and invited Energy-X stakeholders on the structuring of future research calls and investment needs to fulfil the entire SUNRISE Roadmap by 2030.

Friday, 7 February 2020 PM, 9.00 - 13.00

Blueprint – “compromise” scenario

Aim: Collect input from SUNRISE consortium members and invited Energy-X stakeholders on the structuring of future research calls and investment needs to fulfil prioritized parts of the SUNRISE Roadmap by 2030.

B. Public meetings / SUNERGY kick-off

Part 1 : SUN-ERGY policy lunch event at the European Parliament

‘Decarbonising Europe: How large-scale R&I initiatives on fossil-free fuels and chemicals can contribute to the European Green Deal’

5 February 13.00 – 14.30

European Parliament I Brussels (by invitation only), Moderator: Joanna Kargul, University of Warsaw, SUNERGY Executive Board

13.00 – 13.10	Opening statements - Morten Helveg Petersen, MEP, Denmark
13.10 – 13.40	Keynote: Helene Chraye and Mark van Stiphout, the European Commission
13.40 – 13.55	SUNERGY, the way forward - Bert Weckhuysen, SUNERGY coordinator, Utrecht University
13.55 – 14.10	The industry perspective - Maximilian Fleischer, Chair SUNERGY Industrial Board, Siemens AG
14.10 – 14.25	Questions from the audience
14.25 – 14.30	Closing remarks - Morten Helveg Petersen, MEP, Denmark

Part 2: SUNERGY public kick-off event

‘Fossil-free fuels and chemicals for a climate-neutral Europe’

February 5, 16.00 – 18.00

TownHall Europe, Square de Meeus, Brussels

15.30 – 16.00	Registration and coffee
16.00 – 16.10	Welcome (Bert Weckhuysen, SUNERGY coordinator, Utrecht University)
16.10 – 16.30	SUNERGY (Frédéric Chandezon, SUNERGY deputy coordinator, CEA)
16.30 – 17.00	Perspective from industry (Jan Mertens, ENGIE)
17.00 – 17.30	Perspective from European Commission (Peter Dröll, Director Prosperity, DG RTD)
17.30 – 17.55	Q&A
17.55 – 18.00	Wrap-up
18.00 – 20.00	Networking reception

February 6, 9.00 – 14.00

The Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU, Brussels, 21 Rue Montoyer, Brussels

9.00 – 9.30	Registration and coffee
9.30 – 9.40	Opening Address (Johannes Bade, Head of Unit Higher Education, Research and the Arts, Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU)
9.40 – 10.00	SUN-ERGY Vision (Bert Weckhuysen, SUNERGY coordinator, Utrecht University)
10.00 – 11.00	SUN-ERGY Implementation approach - Ramp-up phase leading to a large-scale initiative (Gabriele Centi, ERIC) - Starting point of implementation: key elements of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X roadmaps (Hervé Bercegol, CEA) - Q&A
11.00 – 11.30	Coffee Break
11.30 – 11.50	Presentation Photo-contest winner (Amedeo Agosti, University of Bologna)
11.50 – 13.00	Short presentations by recently awarded projects in the area followed by a round table discussion (Moderator: Joanna Kargul, Warsaw University): - CE-NMBP-25-2019: Photocatalytic synthesis, awarded project 'DistributEd Chemicals And fuels production from CO2 in photoelectrocatalytic Devices' (Siglinda Perathoner, ERIC) - LC-SC3-RES-29-2019: Converting Sunlight to storable chemical energy, awarded project 'Novel photo-assisted systems for direct Solar-driven redUctioN of CO2 to energy rich CHEMicals' (Huub de Groot, Leiden University) - ITN-2019: Awarded project 'Training the next generation of scientists in solar chemicals for a sustainable Europe by hybrid molecule/semiconductor devices' (Pau Farràs, NUI Galway) - ITN-2016: Awarded project 'Electrochemical Conversion of Renewable Electricity into Fuels and Chemicals' (Petr Krtil, J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry)

- LC-SC3-CC-1-2018: Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) aspects of the Clean-Energy Transition, awarded project 'Collective action Models for Energy Transition and Social Innovation' (Merce Almuni, VITO-Energyville)

13.00 – 14.00 Lunch

3. Minutes of the meetings

PART 1: Minutes consortium meetings

Dates: 3-4/02/2020

Location: EERA, Brussels

SUNRISE Final Consortium Meeting

Minutes

Session 1: Deliverables

Monday, 3 February 2020

Opening words by Huub de Groot (LU, SUNRISE CSA coordinator)

Huub de Groot/ UL congratulates the consortium for the autonomous attitude in organizing the work and delivering the results. *Huub* informs the consortium about an open session for an amendment to the Grant Agreement, including a two-month-extension to SUNRISE. *Frédéric Chandezon (CEA)* thinks the extension offers some flexibility but should not delay in working on the future initiative SUNERGY. All agree the work should continue as planned, following the original schedule. The due dates of the three deliverables are shifted to 30 April 2020: D2.3 the fully developed innovation and exploitation plan, D4.2 terms of reference, and D5.3 the final report.

One of the key outputs of SUNRISE is the roadmap. A scientific narrative would be needed for the industrial companies to consider investing. During the sessions on Thursday and Friday, we will also look at the investment scenarios that can cover (parts of) the roadmap. Investing in low TRL can only be justified for technologies with a very high market potential, which is the case of the SUNRISE technologies. *Huub* reminds the consortium that at the DG ENER meeting on 24 October 2019, EC officials suggested the consortium to come up with two investment scenarios: a compromise scenario covering priorities of the Roadmap – and a full-scale scenario, covering the entire roadmap.

Announcement Max Fleischer: Siemens Energy has been created under the Siemens holding, Max is now part of this new company. Due to complex and lengthy formalities to change the representation in SUNRISE, it was decided that Max, together with Thomas Soller will continue to work on SUNRISE.

Deliverables WP 1 Strategy and structuring

D1.2 Roadmap (Hervé Bercegol, CEA)

The work on the Roadmap finished last November. Since then, corrections and comments were received from various partners (CEA, Empa, Helmholtz, Leiden University, Siemens Netherlands and Turku University) and the supporters community (among others Climeworks TU Delft, TNO, TU Berlin, Univ. of Paris). The main document was corrected and the appendices were changed/expanded.

The Roadmap includes three approaches with very different maturity levels, which posed challenges in terms of alignment. Some of the Roadmap goals are included in the manifesto. The goals, as presented in the manifesto, are discussed further.

Discussion:

- The goal for **2025** is to make (liquid) fuel from CO₂ and sunlight on a house roof. This goal appears realistic and there is no efficiency target associated to it.
- **2030**: run a mid-sized airport (Copenhagen) and its flights entirely fossil-free. There seem to be on-going discussions in Energy-X between DTU and the Copenhagen airport. **Action point Frédéric/CEA**: ask Energy-X about the status of the discussions.

Huub/UL: There are similar on-going discussions in The Netherlands, at Schiphol, with TU Delft. The impetus to bring this technology to maturity is very strong, 2025 may be even more realistic. *Joanna Kargul (UW)*: There are existing private partnerships in place, e.g. airport of Rotterdam aiming at a consumption of 1000 L renewable jet fuel/day by 2021.

- **2050**: use artificial photosynthesis and renewable energy to produce carbon-neutral fuels and chemicals across Europe. *Hervé* shows a calculation for the production of Jet fuels with PV + electrolysis, assuming: CO₂ capture at 9 GJ/t CO₂. At a solar-to-electric efficiency of 15% (conservative figure for today) and electric-to-fuel efficiency of 40%, CO₂ capture eats up 1/5 of the harvested solar energy, giving a final total yield of 5% Solar-to-fuel. The efficiency of CO₂ capture must increase in parallel with the improvement of conversion processes. If electric-to-fuel efficiency reaches 55% in 2030, with PV panels delivering 30% Solar-to-electric, an energy consumption of CO₂ capture decreased to 5 GJ/t CO₂ would keep its energy demand below 1/5 of the total (then the solar-to-fuel efficiency would eventually reach 14%). *Huub/UL* criticizes this methodology, because efficiencies are misleading and photon-to-product yields are the correct approach to avoid beginners' mistakes with ergodicity. Moreover, according to *Huub*, incremental approaches are not sufficiently disruptive for a flagship or similar large-scale initiative. For formic acid, the inappropriate approach leads to assumed (fixed) efficiencies that are 40% solar (PV) to electric and 64% electric-to-product (25% solar-to-product) and 5 GJ/t CO₂ captured. Huub observes that this implies connecting two Carnot cycles, which is what SUNRISE aims to avoid. In the end what makes the difference is the rate at which the conversion takes place. At thermodynamic equilibrium there is no conversion of CO₂ and no concentration energy required. The higher the rate, the more free energy will be needed for the concentration of CO₂. A slower process over a large area (via decentralized devices) thus offers a more favourable balance between energy stored and energy wasted than the current processes with electric concentration to high density, albeit at a higher materials cost. Avoiding two

separate Carnot stages would require a new class of materials that can act as both absorber and catalyst. *Max/Siemens* agrees the currently available way to convert solar to products with PV – electric concentration – Electrolysis – Thermocatalysis is doable albeit very limited in energetic conversion efficiency (due to the need for high CO₂ concentration as well), whereas the new approaches looking at the direct solar-to-product conversion promise more efficient conversion, by circumventing some Carnot limits with nonadiabatic strategies that allow for intermediate steps with near-unity yield at very low energy loss.

Frédéric reminds the consortium that the SUNRISE roadmap was highly praised by the EC officials, as well as by the Energy-X representatives. The future SUNERGY roadmap should follow a similar approach and format.

D1.3 Blueprint (Leif Hammarström, UU)

Leif presents the draft Blueprint document (also on the *Plaza under Library* → *Deliverables* → *D.1.3 Blueprint*).

Action all partners: review the document, especially on the competences listed – and complete if necessary.

Huub: There are also scientific “trends”, such as in the case for Electrochemistry. To avoid over- or underrepresentation for a specific competence, we should refer to the European competitive edge and mention the most representative organizations. **Action Stefan/Helmholtz**, to review the list together with Leif and make it open for further inclusion.

Suggestions from partners:

- Refer to EIT InnoEnergy
- Mention ESFRI = European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, (<https://www.esfri.eu/>).
- ICIQ and ISE-Fraunhofer should also be mentioned, as test centers on solar fuels,
- Investigate if EERA or AMPEA have an overview of all relevant infrastructures for solar fuels **Action Frédéric/CEA and Anita/EERA** to investigate.
- Policy-making and legislative aspects. The challenge is to mobilize the investors and governments (via e.g. Green bonds) – **action Huub/UL** to provide text input.

Remark *Max/Siemens*: the document looks rather conservative. We may need to mention the more progressive, emerging competences that are needed for the development of slow, low-concentration processes for C capture, to overcome the thermodynamic limits. *Huub/UL* agrees we need to refer to the competences needed to develop materials that can capture CO₂ from atmosphere and catalyze its conversion directly → **Action Huub/UL** to provide input to Leif (and Ann Magnuson) on far-reaching competences for direct C capture and conversion.

On the same line: some wording is rather soft, such as the evaluation of a possibility to set-up a strategic advisory board. **Action Frédéric/CEA** to strengthen the wording of this paragraph.

Section 5 (currently “Business models”) could be renamed “Investment scenarios”. According to Huub, the idea of this section is to provide a short narrative for the investors, highlighting the main scientific hurdles, where they are positioned in the roadmap in terms of TRL and timelines, as well as the associated investment needs. To progress on

this, we will need the input of **Peter Ellis/JM** and **Philippe Jacques/EMIRI** during the workshops on 6-7/02/20.

Other comments:

- The pictures in section 5 were taken from the Roadmap, but lack a timeline axis, this must be put back. **Action Huub** to provide a text on the innovation pipeline.
- *Hervé/CEA* observes that also in case of bio (algae) conversion, half of the energy is used by the microorganisms, so that must also be accounted for. *Leif/UU*: if the CO₂ concentration is not limiting concentrating CO₂ by microorganism is basically cost-free.¹

D1.1 Consolidated vision (Nicola Armaroli, CNR)

The vision of SUNRISE has not changed since the beginning of the project. The three targets of SUNRISE are: 1. Solar fuels (H₂, ethanol); 2. Solar chemicals (*e.g.* N-based fertilizers) and 3. Removing and recycling CO₂ from the atmosphere (long-term, 2050).

Nicola expresses concern that the direct conversion is now out of the text of the large-scale IA call. Frédéric mentions an RIA call, open for the entire spectrum of SUNRISE technologies (to be discussed in the WP 4 Governance session).

WP 2: Innovation and Exploitation (I)

D2.1 Innovation process (Arne Roth, Fraunhofer)

Transition to a circular economy is beyond the normal commercial context. Challenges:

- Long (> 10 years) innovation cycles in the chemical industry
- High investments required
- Renewables are generally more costly than fossil-based technologies
- High risks

A SUNRISE Innovation process (SIP) was designed to provide a framework that could maximize the prospects of solar-to-products technologies – in the form of “valleys” (following the model of the Silicon valley) as local nodes to support innovation and foster a business-friendly environment. The innovation team must be part of the governance structure. The Innovation process includes: idea generation, evaluation & selection, experimentation, commercialization, and implementation. The last step is often the most challenging, as it requires the highest investment (*e.g.* to build pilot plants) and lengthy timelines. Next steps:

- Creation of a SIP team
- Selection of topics/content of webinars/forums
- Selection of SUNRISE nodes
- Information flow and IP matters (D2.2. and D2.3)

D2.2 Innovation structure (Arne Roth on behalf of Peter Ellis, JM)

¹ If CO₂ concentration is slow, its costs are low, but it is not cost free, unless ergodicity is broken by *e.g.* selfassembly, adsorption or condensation, in which case one has to pay for it at a later stage.

The current status: IPR guidelines were drafted, consistent with the practices used in H2020. The benefits of information sharing must be balanced with the needs to generate commercial partnerships.

The deliverable D2.2 is an interim report leading to D2.3, and is currently available in a draft form. A working meeting follows on Wednesday 5/02, with all involved partners, to refine and consolidate the document.

An open innovation structure implies that IP is shared by all members of the consortium. *Huub/UL* proposes a step-wise methodology to share IP with the priority to the consortium members, by allowing private partners to buy IP within a project, where after it is offered to other projects and then to the outside world. According to Peter (JM) this would lead to highly constrained grant agreements, which is, according to industry, probably not worth the trouble. *Huub* emphasizes that we may nevertheless transfer from an economy of scale IP model with highly protected synergistic patent portfolios to a farming IP model with extensive licensing. To allow for this, IP should be transferred to distributors licenses. Those are not necessarily in the project (RIA or IA) that generated the IP.

Several challenges were identified for the exploitation. The innovation protocols change during product lifecycles, from low to high TRLs. In terms of science-to-business exploitation, no one-size fits all requirements for business, this depends on the market.

Discussion:

Thomas Soller/Siemens suggests to address the product development cycle too. Arne agrees, Thomas will be involved in the workshop planned on Wed 5/02.

Green bonds: not yet addressed in the innovation deliverables (D2.2 mentions de-risking).

Hervé: even when the technology progresses to high TRL, you need basic science to optimize the devices. Special mechanisms must be created in order to allow for systematic innovation. Arne agrees, but thinks this is already addressed in the document.

IA (Innovation Action) call: Frédéric reminds the partners that the IA call and other calls to be released are still competitive calls, and other consortia can also apply.

Frédéric indicates that SUNERGY has to be an umbrella to share results (also failures, as pointed out by *Hervé*), and provide a good forum to advance the field. Agreements among different projects might be made.

Finally, *Huub* acknowledges the contributions of all attendees and closes the session.

Anita gives indications for dinner.

End of day 1.

Tuesday, 4 February 2020

WP 2: Innovation and Exploitation (II)

D2.3 Innovation and exploitation plan (Thomas Soller, Siemens)

Thomas Soller presents the plans for the writing of the deliverable D2.3. Exploitation depends on regulatory and market boundary conditions. There are three main scenarios for market deployment, debated at the 13th Forum Energiewende, 20 January 2020:²

- “Modern jazz” Market developing freely and the most efficient solution naturally emerges;

² Background document on the Plaza, under Meetings → 2020 → Consortium_3-4Feb20_Bruss.

- “Unfinished symphony” – when policy or legislations guide the market development through economic incentives;
- “Hard rock scenario” – green technologies driven by individual state policies (not preferred).

Siemens was encouraged by the German policy makers to define a scenario for green energy technology development, choosing between the two considered scenarios (the first two above). This approach may also be useful for SUNRISE.

According to these scenarios, global energy emissions are estimated by the World Energy Council to lead to a global temperature increase with *ca* 2,5 °C, unfinished symphony: 2-2,3 °C, whereas the last scenario can lead to a temperature increase of more than 3 °C.

Discussion:

Huub/UL suggests to start from the SUNRISE vision and assess which scenario can lead to a certain percent of circularity. We need to look at the opportunities offered by the European context: cities as support for the deployment of new technologies, availability and willingness to pay for it with the European citizens.

Frédéric/CEA: it seems we favour a small-scale approach for circularity when you consider cities.

Leif/UU: We are living in a globalized world, any exchange at regional levels is in fact global, we cannot neglect exchanges with other regions. Defining local circularity can only be done in a global context.

Huub/UL: we need to decouple economic growth from the use of resources. The DG ENER representatives asked us to propose scenarios for our technology and insisted to refer to the current policy documents, such as the SET Plan. Nevertheless, the views of the World Energy Council are more inclusive and representative, as compared to *e.g.* the International Energy Agency (IEA) that may be considered biased towards the oil industry (*Nicola/CNR* agrees). *Max/Siemens*: indeed, the discussion with the representatives of the World Energy Council was meant to provide us with an open perspective free from individual national interests.

Frédéric/CEA: Since we are compelled to come up with a governance scheme with strong industrial participation, the instruments need to be properly structured: we are doing this in consultation with Energy-X.

Huub/UL: exploration puts a limit on how fast fossil resources can be exploited. We are proposing a paradigm shift, from exploration to manufacturing change, and PV was the first technology to achieve this. Energy transitions are assumed to take 30 years. If we manage to circumvent the thermodynamical limits of the current state of the art practices in CO₂ conversion and find a way to manufacture devices to directly absorb and convert CO₂ to products, we can significantly accelerate the energy transition.

Further, Thomas presents an overview of the IP-related concepts addressed in D2.2 and the need to work them out in D2.3. For example:

- The IP Management Committee (IPMC) may need further detailing.
- Defining IPR building blocks for the SUNRISE consortium may need to refine the ownership strategies for joint results, set-up joint ownership rules according to state-of-the art models such as DESCAs, MCARD etc.
- Define the role of the consortium in the alignment of various IP strategies and facilitation of innovation exchange among projects. Should this be part of the Governance?

Discussion:

Max/Siemens: Who will pay for the investment related to maintaining the relevant patents? We can propose a structural instrument, such as a European patent pool or database that can maintain EU patents relevant to the circular economy. This can be funded with EC support for the first period, before generating benefits (via licensing) to self-sustain itself. *Artur Braun/Empa*: This may entail changing IP protection legislation. *Hervé/CEA*: Patent laws should however not hinder the development of green technologies. *Huub/UL*: the research organizations developing the technologies take on the patenting cost for the first stage, and sell the patents to the interested industrial parties. A revolving fund can ensure the mechanism to commercialize the technologies. We may also define procedures to screen the publications for IP by the Partnership, in an open innovation ecosystem. However, this may make small companies reluctant to participate. The complexity of joint ownership situations may slow down the cooperation within the Partnership (remark *Leif/UU*).

Action point: Max/Siemens and Huub/UL to discuss with the EC officials (such as Philippe Schild) possible options to ensure long-term funding for SUNRISE innovations. Finally, effective exploitation strategies are discussed. The failure to commercialize technology ventures is largely related to a poor understanding of the market. We may need to:

- Define a baseline/metrics for all projects;
- Clarify and visualize the link between technology and product development, including involved stakeholders (from TRL 1 to 9), according to different market scenarios. These scenarios however do not account for disruptive developments.

Joanna/UW proposes to look at very disruptive examples, such as Apple. We can definitely capitalize on the societal need to address climate change and secure a future for the future generation. This need was less prevalent 10 years ago, now the momentum is there, and time can favor a disruptive approach. Comment *Artur/Empa*: but what about the others who have never made it?

Huub/UL: the energy market is very large, and the level of investments there are far beyond our comprehension. Scientific advisory board member Dan Nocera from Harvard suggested that private stakeholders in those sectors we are aiming to provide substitute technologies for will continuously inquire about the market potential of the SUNRISE technologies as their principle due diligence process, to decide if they should step in at low TRL levels in what may convert their existing infrastructure and business models to adopt with disruptive technologies:

- Replacement of fossil fuels;
- Replacement of fossil-based chemicals;
- Manufacturing equipment (refineries etc.).

Huub/UL: Assuming a hypothetical budget of 1 B€ and two major demonstrator targets such as the high TRL airport and the lower TRL roof, also assuming redundancy (several projects working on the same goal), one can define the needs for a number of RIA and IA addressing the targets, aligned across TRLs within the considered budget boundaries. Our challenge is to present a credible plan to achieve it.

Philippe Jacques (EMIRI): It may be interesting to have a discussion with EIT InnoEnergy, which is coaching project teams in order to build their business case, in such a way that details can be worked out later, at the project level.

WP 3: Dissemination, Communication and Education (Laura Lopez, ICIQ)

D3.1 Dissemination Plan

The project has reached a large number of supporters. The SUNRISE community (including newsletter subscribers and social media followers) counts 2.125 members. However, reaching further the general public and the policy makers remains challenging. The main dissemination and communication tools were deployed with the involvement of the consortium partners.

Communication highlights for the last months include: Lunch meeting at DG ENER (24 October 2019), Public poll for the SUNERGY name, the national stakeholder meetings, participation stand at the SET Plan conference and COP 25, SUNERGY photo contest and SUNERGY kick-off meeting.

D3.2 Website & App

The SUNRISE website is the main online tool for communication, supplemented by social media channels. A test app version was developed by Tobias Gärtner for scientific information exchange. However, this tool may need to be re-purposed.

Next actions, discussion:

Laura mentions that there will be efforts to maintain the communication on SUNRISE, however the extent of that depends on the resources allocated. A new budget must be drafted to cover the follow-up communication and dissemination actions, related to SUNERGY (discussion on-going with Energy-X, Bert Weckhuysen). *Frédéric* indicates that funding may come via a new CSA, however plans are currently unclear.

Web traffic: 1600 average monthly sessions, of 5 pages and 4 minutes/session, on average. Events such as the participation to COP25 led to a significant increase of visits on the website. Visits come primarily from the US, France and Germany. There is also intense activity from the US on twitter. There is an issue with Facebook: first, it requires payment. Also, after a few months of running, the SUNRISE page was labeled as a page with socially-relevant (politically sensitive) content, which subjects it to content reviews and censorship. Based on the current discussions on the dissemination and communication plan, focusing on Instagram for SUNERGY instead of Facebook appears the best option. The SUNERGY Instagram account is already open, as it was used for the photo contest.

D3.3 Resources

Communications resources were developed to support the dissemination efforts: mugs, posters, roll-ups, leaflets, infographics and videos.

D3.4 Data Management Plan

A Data Management Plan was drafted, describing the SUNRISE strategy and practices regarding the open access to scientific publications etc. The project outputs (project reports and publications, dissemination and outreach materials, deliverables) will all be made publicly available on the public repository ZENODO, in line with the Open access dissemination strategy.

Next actions:

- Set main objectives and actions for the Dissemination and Communication plan;
- Update the SUNRISE app with recent publications and make a final survey on its future development among consortium members;
- Upload all output materials to Plaza and ZENODO;

- Facts and figures infographics;
- Digital story: a wrap-up about the full project.

Action Laura to follow-up with the consortium.

WP 4 Governance

Anita Schneider/EERA presented a briefing for the policy-makers, based on the manifesto, to be printed out and distributed to the participants from the EP event on February 5th.

D4.1 Governance Plan (Frédéric Chandezon, CEA)

Frédéric/CEA presents “the path to SUNERGY”, the succession of steps and events leading up to the merging of the two CSA initiatives. The present governance structure of the SUNERGY initiative involves a Scientific Executive Board and an Industrial Board (under definition and chaired by Maximilian Fleischer from Siemens), supported by ICIQ, EERA and DTU. There is no Strategic Advisory Board in SUNERGY.

Comments partners:

- *Artur Braun/Empa*: There was a lack of democratic vote and selection for example when assigning members to Boards.
- *Philippe Jacques/EMIRI*: It only makes sense to discuss the organization once funding is guaranteed.

The D4.1 document presents a scenario, a timeline and an organizational structure of a SUNERGY European large-scale research and innovation initiative. Main developments are presented:

- A key document was “Orientations towards the first Strategic Plan for Horizon Europe”. In this document, only the old flagships are acknowledged. At page 22, it is stated: “*Preparatory actions supported under the FET Flagships part of Horizon 2020 will also e.g. inform the work on missions, co-funded/co-programmed partnerships and regular calls for proposals*”. The reference to co-funded partnerships may be related to the Clean Energy Transition (CET).
- Five missions were launched for Horizon Europe. While not ignoring them, Frédéric/CEA thinks we should not target missions, the way they are supposed to operate is not clear either. Getting involved in the current missions as they are defined can lead to fragmentation. *Huub* mentions there is a large budget associated to missions. *Philippe Jacques/EMIRI* shares Frédéric’s opinion, it seems missions will likely act as “debating clubs”. Nevertheless, should there be a call for new missions, SUNERGY will submit a proposal.
- A joint (SUNRISE & Energy-X) proposition for a Partnership (FCM: Fossil Free Fuels, Chemicals and Materials for a Circular Economy) was submitted to the various rounds of consultations on Partnerships, and raised awareness among the national and European stakeholders. Although dismissed for 2020, there is the possibility for a Partnership as of 2024. The three forms of partnerships (co-programmed, co-funded or institutionalized) are presented, with their particular features. Co-programmed and institutionalized partnerships allow public-private partnerships. Institutionalized partnerships receive budget from the European Commission, who commissions the decision-making to the partnership consortium, whereas co-programmed partnerships work with the mandated representatives of the consortium to decide on the priorities for the open calls.

Institutionalized partnerships are not very flexible instruments adapted for established communities and with legally binding agreements. Revising roadmap and objectives and entering new partners is thus quite difficult and requires amendments. According to *Frédéric*, a co-programmed partnership (such as the current contractual Public-Private Partnerships, cPPPs, e.g. SPIRE) seems to be the most suitable option for SUNERGY. There are some changes in Horizon Europe with respect to the organization of the cPPPs. Comment *Philippe Jacques*: the co-funded partnerships allow for additional budget from the Member States. *Huub* points out the difficulty of obtaining commitment from Industry and the Member States. SUNRISE has promised a credible path towards getting this commitment. *Frédéric* indicates that it is possible to have both industry and MS in a co-programmed partnership but following information obtained by *Philippe Jacques* from EC contacts, it is not yet clear how at the moment.

The plan proposed by the Governance team:

- Short-term (February – December 2020): coordination and community building; implement the blueprint and prepare the ramp-up phase
- “Ramp-up” phase (2021 – end 2023): roadmapping, monitoring, implement the SUNERGY roadmap
- Long-term (as of 2024): co-programmed public-private partnership

Discussion:

- *Stefan/FZJ* mentions that sources from the German NCP indicate that a second round of partnerships cannot be taken for granted. The willingness to fully reopen the procedure seems to be limited. Therefore, the future proposal needs to be extremely convincing.
- *Artur/Empa* expresses concern that the supporters cannot understand the governance mechanisms. They need clear topic areas to work on. To achieve critical mass, *Leif/UU* points out the importance of providing coordinated inputs to the EC (at MS levels, but also with AMPEA, Mission Innovation).
- *Huub/UL* urges the current SUNRISE consortium not to underestimate the importance of producing a high-level output, with funding from the on-going SUNRISE CSA. It is very important to proactively promote topics into the EU-launched calls.
- *Joanna/UW* stresses that the consortium must become active in formulating the calls not only giving feedback to the content of calls. *Frédéric/CEA* suggests organizing writing clubs (also joint with Energy-X) – **action Frédéric**.
- *Philippe Jacques/EMIRI*: The goals for 2030 are supposed to be realized by the industrial community, however the governance structure proposed seems to be driven by the research community. In order to obtain commitment from the EC, the governance structure should allow for industrial participation.

A governance structure is proposed for the “ramp-up” phase of SUNERGY, aligning coordination via CSA, ERA-NET and implementation (RIA, IA, including a large IA project).

- *Huub/UL*: An ERA-NET may be a step backwards, as it leads to fragmentation. *Laura* shares this opinion. The idea about incorporating running projects in the emerging SUNERGY initiative (as per suggestion *Laurent Baraton/ Engie*) prompts *Huub* with the idea of a scheme evaluating the outputs of running EU-funded projects (on a voluntary basis), as a way of claiming authority in the field

with a self-invented Quality and Impact Assurance structure. EU can demand the newly-funded projects to enter a cooperation agreement, as is done already with e.g. Batteries.

- *Frédéric/CEA*: Although some things seemed to have been decided before we had the chance to act (such as the first round of partnerships), the EC is in the process of shaping Horizon Europe, so opportunities may arise even before 2024. *Philippe Jacques/EMIRI*: there are discussions on the Batteries partnership (decided two years ago), already for more than one year, to define the priorities.
- *Leif/UU*: We should then align the targets for SUNERGY so that they are in line with the start of Partnership of 2024, for example amend the dates in the Manifesto to “start+1 year”, +5 years, +10 years.
- *Hervé/CEA*: Apart from the dichotomy between the compromise scenario and the “all-in/all-out” scenario, there may also be an opportunistic/realistic scenario. Although the compromise scenario is largely based on the plans for the second round of partnerships, there may be new opportunities offered by the Green Deal, targeting 2030, which is unlikely to be postponed.
- *Nicola/CNR*: We were not successful so far with the Partnerships and Missions. Perhaps we are missing a more direct path towards securing a large-scale initiative. *Stefan/FZJ*: The Flagships stemmed from DG Connect because this is how it has been developed at the EC level, diverting budgets originally devoted for IT-related topics to energy and other topics.
- *Huub/UL*: the EC operates via the member states, there is no decision made in Brussels. To succeed, we must make our plan and using the instruments available at EU level.
- *Hervé/CEA*: asks what are the right actions to take to engage with politicians? *Huub/UL*: come up with a full-throttle scenario that makes sense and present to politicians. We should also have a compromise scenario, and make clear why the better plan is the preferred one. *Frédéric/CEA*: we must also align our goals with Energy-X, to be one voice towards the European decision-makers.

A follow-up CSA “Breakthrough zero-emissions energy generation for full decarbonization” was proposed in the FET programme on Dec. 19/Jan. 20, coupled to a RIA topic.

According to *Frédéric/CEA*, the CSA was dropped by the EC, where the final answer from DG Connect was that they cannot support the CSA initiative, motivating that one CSA cannot receive special treatment over the others selected at the same call for new FET Flagships. Nevertheless, the RIA plan is still valid, for low-TRL technologies (budget for three projects, at 4-4,5 Meuro/project). The call will be published in March, and close on June 23rd, most likely single-stage. *Huub/UL* advises to organize joint consortia with Energy-X.

Action point Frédéric/CEA and Laura/ICIQ: circulate information about the coming RIA call among the supporters community.

Another CSA topic was discussed by Energy-X with DG RTD, “Creation of an innovation community for solar fuels and chemicals”. Status to be checked with Gabriele Centi (Energy-X), **Action point Frédéric/CEA**.

Discussion:

- *Max/Siemens* suggests to label upcoming initiatives “SUNERGY”, this may increase visibility and increase chances of success (assuming excellent proposals are submitted).
- *Philippe Jacques/EMIRI* informs the consortium that 1 Billion euro will be allocated to 8-12 calls (IA) under H2020, closing June.³ This is the case for the IA call under discussion with Energy-X.
- An action point **Frédéric/CEA** is to investigate other opportunities from the Green Deal.

Innovation Action call for a Large-scale initiative:

The tentative call deadline is on August 2020, TRL 4-7. The topic needs final approval from Member States via NMBP/Strategic Programme Committee.

- *Max/Siemens*: these calls are targeting device demonstration at several tons/year. Very interesting for Siemens, Shell, Total. Nevertheless, the funding effort is very significant (10-30 Meuro per proposal).
- *Huub/UL*: an IA call is appropriate for current technologies, mainly those coming out of Energy-X. The direct conversion technologies would benefit from a series of RIA calls. On direct conversion, the algae conversion would be suitable for upscaling.

There was a request from Energy-X to assign a member from SUNRISE to the writing team for this IA call. The name of Vincent *Artero/CEA* was proposed. Leif Hammarström and Ann Magnuson/UU were considered, they declined. **All agree that Vincent Artero (CEA) should be included in this team.**

Stefan/FZJ: perhaps we can consider platform-like calls with smaller-scale projects on lower TRL technologies, addressing topics aligned with the core IA topics and giving the opportunity to utilize the large scale infrastructure built by the IA-demonstrator (*e.g.* testing a bench-top pilot at the demo-site).

Nicola/CNR: As per info from Gabriele Centi, there will be a single IA call, large (100 Million euro) and it is considered that some of this budget is dedicated to low-TRL research. Nevertheless, there will not be multiple calls. The call is indeed oriented towards large industrial demonstrators.

Next Governance event: meeting on SUNERGY Governance, on 19 February, from 10.30-16.00, at DECHEMA (Governance leader in Energy-X) - in Frankfurt. The participation of representative Energy-X members is again uncertain, this remains a challenge.

D4.2 Terms of Reference (Max Fleischer, Siemens)

Why does the industry need an orchestrated R&D initiative?

There is an overall agreement that the Energy System is going to change. Cooperation will emerge from traditionally separated sectors, towards a cyclic energy and carbon system. Opportunities:

- Unprecedented markets for industries (already showed for PV and wind)
- Industry needs an orchestrated link with academia

³ This refers to the special Green Deal call. According to the latest information (February 2020) the due date will be shifted to early 2021, but the call will still be part of the H2020 framework.

- The European industry should lead on the manufacturing of the components and assembly of the systems.

Max shows a comparison to the US initiative JCAP, funded by the Department of Energy. The focus of JCAP is the direct conversion. JCAP is organized with a governance board (nine persons with management functions, from the participating institutions), a scientific advisory board (seven persons from non-contributing academic institutions + one industrial partner) and a strategic advisory board (eight persons from renowned institutions, not necessarily scientists). Max joined the strategic advisory board, which only gives advice to the scientific board. The structure of JCAP provided inspiration in the set-up of the Industrial Board of SUNERGY.

General tasks of the Industrial Board:

- Align the R&D programme with the industrial/economic needs on short- and long-term;
- Give credibility to the SUNERGY initiative, and mobilize industrial participation;
- Generate proposals for implementation.

The industrial board will work on market needs and forecasts, in order to steer scientific developments. It will also provide inputs on pricing for synthetic molecules, expected quantities and economic needs (CAPEX, OPEX, efficiencies). It will also work with the investors on making the output of the research bankable. Also proposed: reviewing the content of the proposed research projects, from the market perspective (time to market and acceptance). *Frédéric/CEA* thinks such a review function should rather take place upstream, at call level.

The composition of the Industrial Board (chaired by Max Fleischer, Chief expert energy at **Siemens Energy**) is also presented. The following are considered as members (the confirmed ones in bold letters): Covestro, VICAT, **Haldor Topsee** (from the Energy-X network), **Engie**, **CO2 Value**, EMIRI (from SUNRISE). Other propositions: petrochemical company (Total, Shell, Repsol). **DECHEMA**, SMEs such as Ineratec, Avantium or Photanol.

- Proposed by partners (*Joanna/UW* and *Yagut/Turku*): Nestle.
- Proposed by *Philippe Jacques/EMIRI*: identify and involve companies from Eastern European countries.
- Other propositions: Austrian oil company OMV, ArcelorMittal.

Action partners: propose companies and send contacts to Max.

End of the meeting

PART 2: Minutes Blueprint meetings

SUNRISE Blueprint Meetings

Minutes

Sessions:	Feb. 6 - 15:00 – 18:00:	“Full Scenario”
	Feb. 7 - 9:30 – 12:30:	“Compromise Scenario”

Participants:

Huub de Groot (UL, chair) (both days)
Harald Kerp (M2i, minutes) (both days)
Vincent Artero (CEA) (Feb. 6, first hour)
Frédéric Chandezon (CEA) (both days)
Hervé Bercegol (CEA) (both days)
Max Fleischer (Siemens) (both days)
Hélène Lepaumier (Engie) (both days)
Peter Ellis (Johnson Matthey) (Feb. 6, first hour)
Artur Braun (EMPA) (Feb. 6 + Feb. 7, first hour)
Joanna Kargul (UW) (both days)
Matthias Meier (FZ) (both days)
Stefan Baumann (FZ) (both days)
Laura Lopez (ICIQ) (Feb. 7)
Julio Lloret (ICIQ) (both days)
Fernando Fresno (IMDEA) (both days)
Henrik Koch (NTNU) (both days)
Nicola Armaroli (CNR) (both days)
Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (UTU) (both days)
Arne Roth (Fraunh) (both days)
Walter Leitner (Max Planck) (Feb. 7)
Alexis Bazzanella (DECHEMA) (Feb. 7)

Introduction and background - Huub de Groot (LU, SUNRISE CSA coordinator)

Some background is provided on the exercise that is needed to complete the SUNRISE Blueprint document, deliverable 1.3, with investment scenarios. The idea of this section is to provide a short narrative for the private investors, highlighting the main scientific hurdles and technological challenges, where they are positioned in the roadmap in terms of TRL and timelines, as well as the associated investment needs, both public and private. To progress on this, we will need the input of Siemens, Johnson Matthey, Engie, EMIRI, and possibly from selected Energy-X partners who were also invited for the workshop.

The D 1.3 draft document contains a table with an overview of the SUNRISE technologies and TRL goals for 2030, that can be used to collect input on the investment needs and that can serve as a starting point for the session of today. We basically need estimate ranges for both public and private investments needed to push SUNRISE technologies to the targeted TRL levels. The table also includes a preliminary list of companies associated with the different technologies copied from the Technical Appendices of the Roadmap.

Huub proposes the following work flow:

1. For each SUNRISE technology, the number of IA and RIA proposals are estimated needed to reach the targeted TRL goals.

2. Three types of calls will be considered, taking into account the following tentative budgets:
 - Large IA call: 100 M€
 - IA demonstrator: 10 M€
 - RIA call: 5 M€
3. For each call the percentage of private and public contributions are estimated, leading to total financial ranges for private and public contributions.
4. Additional costs, such as external infrastructural costs and overall management costs, as well as additional funding resources, e.g. the European innovation fund coming from the carbon tax 2020-2030, are also taken into account.
5. Industry indicates the prioritizing criteria, e.g. by outlining the most promising (clusters of) technologies that can be brought to the market by 2030.

The result is a “full scenario” needed to realize the full SUNRISE Vision and “compromise scenario” to realize prioritized parts of the SUNRISE roadmap.

During the sessions, the blueprint D 1.3 draft text was used as a living document in which the earlier mentioned table was continuously updated while important comments were added into the text for elaboration afterwards. Apart from the various comments added to this document a selection of additional remarks, taken from the discussions, are listed below.

February 6 – “Full scenario” session – additional comments:

- Table 1a-1b: Max (Siemens) comments that 4000t of hydrogen supply (for an airport) is a huge quantity given the low mass density. Huub (UL) replies that according to Gabriele Centi, the current focus for the prospective IA is on methanol. Max indicates that first RIA’s are needed for the feasibility, as part of, or followed by an IA.
- Table 1c: ExxonMobil appears to be pushing these ‘green convertors’. Advice is to start again with RIA’s for feasibility, followed by an IA.
- General comment/question by Huub: Shouldn’t we have multiple IA’s in parallel to have various technology options to choose from? The problem arises that probably there aren’t enough EU companies for separate IA’s. Max replies that within the IA’s there should be room for multiple technologies in parallel. Huub agrees that risk mitigation should be within the IA’s. In addition, having parallel tracks provides optimal cross-fertilization for maximum synergy benefits, and delivers de facto an open innovation environment with respect to founding and transferring IP.

Max provides an example that in a power-to-ethanol demonstrator plant it is possible to exchange different electrolyzers. In addition, one should aim for ‘distributed demos’, e.g. plants distributed over countries with low/high solar irradiation intensity.

- Table 4a: The question is asked if new fuel components will encounter issues with regards to the certification of jet fuels, that are very strict? Arne Roth (Fraunhofer) replies that there are standard specs in place for synthetic jet fuel components. The certification process takes many years and costs a couple of M€.
- Table 4b: A couple of demos are already out in the field. However, since these are relatively small-scale, we will aim for “upscaler demo plants”.
- General comment by Huub: In this exercise we develop a “call scheme” over the course of 10 years. We will not add a detailed timeline, we will just show the number of calls needed to reach the SUNRISE goals and identify critical paths to demonstrate the value chain source to final product as the single prioritizing criterion in three priority research directions as indicated below.
- After submitting our blueprint as part of a comprehensive design and description (a.k.a. business plan) the process will be ‘out of our hands’. Next steps will be that DG Connect will review the outcome and engage in rounds of consultations with EU member states.
- Regarding CO₂, Hervé notes that negative emissions technologies are not detailed in the roadmap. Their importance is stated, technical possibilities are discussed, mainly related to construction materials, but we lacked expert views to back-up a technological timeline. However this theme is high on the agenda of CO₂ value Europe.

Max states that CO₂ taxes will have an effect on fossil fuel prices.

- Central management of the projects will need to be steered by a CSA: Assuming a total project portfolio of 1 B€, 1% (10 M€) is assumed to be sufficient to run the CSA (1 M€/year).
- For regional SUNRISE valleys, it is proposed that they could line up with hydrogen valleys. Pillar 3 in Horizon Europe, “Innovative Europe”, could be sourced for the demonstrators when they end successfully. This will be equity financed, *i.e.* not in our budget. In this case, central management will move out as they will operate on their own, central management will only monitor.
- Arne (Fraunhofer) states that an independent group of experts might be needed that accompany, support and connect individual projects with respect to their techno-economic (TEA) and environmental (LCA) assessments. These studies are usually very different and consequently not consistent/comparable. There should be an independent group making sure that methods pursued in TEA/LCA are to a certain extent consistent. Huub refers to our mid-term review and QIA processes, which however do not fully cover the effort proposed here.
- The session is closed with the remark that the full list of calls discussed today corresponds to the “full scenario” for a large-scale research initiative under HE, *i.e.* equivalent to a “full Flagship” under H2020.

February 7 – “Compromise scenario” session – additional comments:

- The session starts with the observation that under HE “private investments” not only contain corporate investments but also investments made by financial institutions in the various member states, like BlackRock.
- Walter Leitner (Max Planck) states that we need to make a distinction between ‘small demonstrators’ (*i.e.* working devices in operating conditions) and ‘full demonstrators’ (*i.e.* large pilot plants), the latter being far more important for companies.
- Laura Lopez (ICIQ) comments that in IA calls companies costs are not fully reimbursed (only up to 70%) which means that actual corporate costs are higher. This has to be taken into account when making the split between private and public investments.
- Leitner comments on CO₂ capture: This is already being done at large scale. We should team up with ongoing efforts and focus on *e.g.* capture + integrated conversion, as proposed in the roadmap.
- Overall the discussion focused on the structuring of the IA / RIA / demonstrator calls, how the technology pipelines feed into the pilot scale demonstrators that are foreseen, and the prioritization of technologies as demanded by industry (see D 1.3 document).
- Since a significant part of the work is focusing on high TRL, we expect to get access to another billion in pillar 3. Helene Lepaumier (Engie) remarks that we should try to access in addition to the innovation fund related to public money coming from the ETS and carbon tax 2020-2030. However, it must be noted that SUNRISE / SUNERGY will only control specific technology developments, such as PEC, and the rest we feed into.

As an end note: As mentioned before the overall plans are being elaborated in a structured way in the draft blueprint document (D 1.3) on the SUNRISE Plaza. The current version of the table and tentative textual notes as drafted during the work sessions are given at the following pages.

SUNRISE technology	Current TRL	TRL target 2030	Companies involved	Private investments (estimate)	Public investments (estimate)	Comments
1. Sustainable hydrogen production						
1a. PV-driven electrolysis of water	4-6	9	Siemens (DE) Nel (N) ITM (UK) Hydrogenics (US, BE) Areva H2Gen (F) Air Liquide (F)	40% C FI p.m.	30% EU 30% MS	IA Demo 2
1b. Photoelectrochemical devices	2-4	5-8	Engie (F) Siemens (DE) SABIC (NL)	20% IA	100% RIA (MS) 80%IA (MS) 100% DD	RIA IA Distributed demo
Transparent baggie systems (microorganisms and photocatalytic systems)	3-4	6-8		40% IA	100% RIA+D 60% IA	RIA lab demo (g/ng)IA
2. Sustainable ammonia production						
2a. Low-emission Haber-Bosch	5-6	9	Yara (N) Casale (CH) Thyssenkrupp (DE) Haldor Topsøes (DK) Siemens (DE)	40%	30% EU 30% MS	IA demo
2b. Electrochemical and plasma-assisted ammonia synthesis	1-2	4-5	n.a.		100% RIA (MS) 100% DP (MS)	2 RIA 1 Demo project
2c. Photoelectrochemical devices	1-2	4-5	n.a.		100% RIA (MS) 100% DP	2 RIA 1 Demoproject
Microorganisms for direct fertilizer production	1-2	4-6			100% RIA (MS) 100% DP	2 RIA 1 Demoproject
3. Sustainable carbon capture						
3a. CO ₂ capture from concentrated sources (concentrate on local value creation) co-adaptation of capture and catalytic conversion into long term storage of Carbon/CO ₂ , targeting Negative Emissions	6-7	9	ENGIE (F) (orchestrate) Gas for Climate consortium ⁴ Fluor (VS) Mitsubishi (J) Siemens (DE) Aker solutions (N) Shell (NL) Solvay (BE) MTR (US) RWE (DE) BASF (DE) LINDE Engineering (IRL-DE-US) LafargeHolcim (F, CH)	30% IA cluster Pipeline will feed into larger DEMOs	70% cluster	IA Demo upscaling link to 4.1 and 4.2 TEAM up with Separate Big 300 ME demo in pillar 3
3b. Direct CO ₂ Capture from the atmosphere	6	8-9	Climeworks (CH) Antecy (NL) Global Thermostat (US) Carbon Engineering (Canada) Ineratec (DE)	30% IA cluster Pipeline will feed into ongoing large demo	70% IA cluster	IA including RIA and Demo (Don't forget low exergy energy) link to 4.1 and 4.2 Don't forget negative emission (1MW scale)
Direct Atmospheric CO ₂ Capture & Conversion including PEC	1-2	5-7		40% IA	100% (MS) 30% IA 30% MS IA	10 RIA 3 Demoproject g/ng IA

⁴ <https://gasforclimate2050.eu/gas-for-climate>

						(don't forget low exergy energy)
4. Sustainable production of commodity chemicals and (jet) fuels						
<i>4a-1. Electrochemical water splitting and thermocatalytic conversion of CO₂</i>	6	9	Airline Global Alliance Powerfuels Aireg (DE) Sunfire (DE) Ineratec (DE)	30%	70%	2 IA clusters FT and methanol) feeding into Demo plant
<i>4a-2. Direct electroreduction of CO₂</i>	3	6	Velocys (US) BASF (DE) Casale (CH)		100% (MS)	4-5 RIA feeding into 2 demo
<i>4b. Direct solar-thermochemical conversion of water and CO₂</i>	4-5	6	Total (F) Synhelion (CH) Toyota (J, BE) Abengoa (ES) Brightsource (Isr) Helpe (Gr)	40% IA	100% (MS) RIA 30% EU IA 30% MS IA	RIA demo g/ng IA upscaler demo plant
<i>4c. Biocatalytic production of carbon-based solar fuels and chemicals</i>	1-6	4-9	Photanol (NL) Ecoduna (AU) Synthetic Genomics (US) Euglena (J) Total (F) Neste (FI)	40% IA	100% RIA (MS) 100% RIA (MS) 30% EU (IA) 30% MS(IA)	8 RIA and 3 demo and 1 small IA Demo plant 100 kt/yr

The demonstrators should all contribute to the decoupling of economic growth from utilization of resources.

All the high efficiency effort should aim for low investment cost and halving the product price compared to fossil resources

IA calls will need very strict programming criteria, RIA are open calls

Another billion in pillar 3, and in addition from the innovation fund (public money coming from the carbon tax 2020-2030), for the highest TRL:

Several pipelines feed into pilot scale production of Jet fuel, 300-500 million revolving fund with airlines

Several pipelines feed into pilot scale production for CO₂ capture from concentrated sources, and CO₂ from the atmospheric capture

Why is this good for Europe/the best for Europe

- Decarbonization of the energy sector paves the way for the other sectors (the supply side argument)
- Why us: we are broad, application oriented, try to develop technology, and we have vertical integration, science - technology - industry over the entire knowledge chain
- Many national projects, now it is time to go European and broaden from photovoltaics (and wind)
- If we don't follow this pathway for defossilization we will lose the primary industry in Europe in what is by far the biggest market
- Priority: demonstrate the value chain source to final product (prioritizing criterion)
- By providing a new paradigm we create room for interpretation for other scientific disciplines and for socio-economic stakeholders

Priority: demonstrate the value chain source to final product (prioritizing criterion)

- Combine water electrolysis with CO₂ capture, this gives the fully integrated value chain.
- Does integration of steps gives better processes (efficiency selectivity/purity, concentration) over the value chain (PV+electrolysis vs PEC vs molecular vs biological)?
- How do we get all the hydrogen to decarbonize - existing - value chains (parliament)

Define groups (Frédéric, with mutual triggering)

Call on house roof (decentralized)
Call on centralized

The tentative budgets for the three types of calls considered are:

- Large IA call: 100 M€
- IA demonstrator: 10 M€
- RIA call: 5 M€

Management: central management/governance/programming/monitoring takes 1% -> CSA

Sunrise valleys: makers join hydrogen valleys, Pillar 3 for the demonstrators when they end successfully. This will be equity financed, not in the budget, central management will move out, they will operate on their own, central management will monitor

Infrastructures: Research infrastructure costs can be charged to projects.

Specification and testing: Bids are called for from centers that will be qualified to do this. Budget: 1M€/yr , 10 M€ total for 1-3 centers associated with PV centers or hydrogen valleys depending on the costs.

Quantitative sustainability analysis is mandatory for every project with go/nogo decisions from the QIA team and program board

Dissemination is in every project, in addition there is global dissemination at the partnership level with the management

Education is part of the central CSA.

Annexes

- 1. Invitation for the SUN-ERGY policy lunch event**
- 2. Invitation for the SUNERGY public kick-off event**
- 3. Press release SUNERGY Kick-off**
- 4. Briefing for politicians**

Annex 1: Invitation for the SUN-ERGY policy lunch event

Dear

You are invited to contribute in person to a high-level lunch discussion on how large-scale, integrated R&I initiatives in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals can contribute to meeting the targets of the Paris Agreement and the ambitions of the European Green Deal.

The event will be held at the European Parliament on 5 February 2020, from 13.00 to 14.30 and will be hosted by Mr. Morten Helveg Petersen, MEP (Denmark). The debate is organized at the initiative of the two European flagship initiatives on energy, SUNRISE and ENERGY-X, which propose clear technological pathways to decarbonize the European industry and society over the next 30 years. SUNRISE and ENERGY-X started under Horizon2020 and have joined forces to prepare a large-scale research and innovation initiative in Horizon Europe, that will complement the scope of existing European partnerships and enable the full decoupling of economic growth from the utilization of resources. Whereas current public-private partnerships all focus on improvements downstream, with limited impact, SUN-ERGY proposes high impact technologies that address the initial stages of the light-to-products and fuel conversion from atmospheric CO₂ at high yield.

The aim of the event is to facilitate the debate between high-level stakeholders on the **focus and timing of the future large-scale initiative in the field of fossil-free fuels and chemicals**. The discussion comes at a time when greater attention to climate and energy issues and ongoing developments at European level (including on Horizon Europe and the Clean Planet for All strategy) offer the right framework for action and a great opportunity to join efforts towards reversing climate change.

We would be very honoured to have you as a speaker, considering your key involvement the European Green Deal. The event is by invitation only, with high-level speakers like yourself, from the European Parliament, European Commission, and the European flagship consortia SUNRISE and ENERGY-X.

We sincerely hope that you will accept our invitation. We will follow-up with your office in the coming days – in the meantime, we remain at your disposal for additional information.

Yours sincerely,

Prof. Jens Nørskov, Technical University of Denmark
Coordinator of ENERGY-X

Prof. Bert Weckhuysen, Utrecht University
Coordinator of SUN-ERGY

Prof. Huub de Groot, Leiden University
Coordinator of SUNRISE

Dr. Frédéric Chandezon, CEA Deputy
Coordinator of SUN-ERGY

SUNRISE (<https://sunriseaction.com>) and **ENERGY-X** (www.energy-x.eu) are two ongoing Horizon 2020 projects (FET Flagship CSA, research area Energy, Environment and Climate Change) selected to prepare a large-scale initiative in the field of fossil-free fuels and chemicals over the course of one year (March 2019 - February 2020). The two projects **will pursue their roadmap actions until February 2020, when they will merge into the SUN-ERGY initiative.**

Annex 2: Invitation for the SUN-ERGY public kick-off event

Update #1
January 21, 2020

SUN-ERGY Kick-off event

February 5, 2020 | Brussels (TownHall, Square de Meeus)

16.00 – 18.00, followed by a reception

February 6, 2020 | Brussels (The Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU, 21 Rue Montoyer)

9.00 – 13.00

Dear Friend,

We would like to invite you to the **kick-off of SUN-ERGY**, a large-scale, integrated R&I initiative in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals. SUN-ERGY stems from two European flagship initiatives on Energy, **SUNRISE** and **ENERGY-X**, which will end in February 2020. They have joined forces to launch SUN-ERGY, a large-scale research initiative in Horizon Europe, that will complement the scope of existing European partnerships and enable the full decoupling of economic growth from the utilization of fossil resources.

During this event, the CSAs SUNRISE and ENERGY-X will present their achievements, and propose their joint vision on decarbonizing the European industry and society over the next 30 years. This initiative comes at a time when greater attention to climate and energy issues and ongoing developments at European level (including on *Horizon Europe* and the *Clean Planet for All* strategy) offer the right framework for action and a great opportunity to join efforts towards reversing climate change.

The kick-off event is organized in two sessions: an afternoon session on 5 February 2020, from 16.00 to 18.00, followed by a reception, and a morning session on 6 February 2020, from 9.00 to 13.00.

You are kindly asked to **confirm your attendance before January 28th** and **register at this link**. An early registration is very much appreciated, in the view of event logistics.

Yours sincerely,

*Prof. Jens Nørskov, Technical University of
Denmark
Coordinator of ENERGY-X*

*Prof. Bert Weckhuysen, Utrecht University
SUN-ERGY coordinator*

*Prof. Huub de Groot, Leiden University
Coordinator of SUNRISE*

*Dr. Frédéric Chandezon, CEA
SUN-ERGY deputy coordinator*

With the friendly support of the Representation
of the State of Hessen to the EU

SUNRISE and **ENERGY-X** are two ongoing Horizon 2020 CSAs (Call FETFLAG-01-2018, research area Energy, Environment and Climate Change) selected to prepare a large-scale initiative in the field of fossil-free fuels and chemicals over the course of one year (March 2019 - February 2020). The two projects will pursue their roadmap actions until February 2020, when they will merge into the **SUN-ERGY** initiative.

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If you need further information send us an email to
contact@sunriseaction.eu & contact@energy-x.eu

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www.sunriseaction.eu & www.energy-x.eu are shaped by

Annex 3: Press release SUNERGY Kick-off

Kick-off of the SUNERGY initiative

Over 100 stakeholders of the Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) SUNRISE and ENERGY-X gathered on February 5-6, 2020 in Brussels for the kick-off meeting of SUNERGY, a large-scale research and innovation (R&I) initiative in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals. Renewable energy experts from academia, industry and policy addressed the current opportunities and challenges towards decarbonizing the European industry and society over the next 30 years.

The launch event was organized in two sessions: a high-level lunch discussion at the European Parliament (EP) on February 5, and a public two-day conference. The TownHall Europe hosted the afternoon session on February 5, while the morning session on February 6 was hosted by the Representation of the State of Hessen to the EU.

Large-scale R&I initiatives to decarbonize Europe

MEP Morten Helveg Petersen hosted the high-level lunch discussion at the EP. Representatives from both initiatives debated on how large-scale R&I initiatives in the area of fossil-free fuels and chemicals can contribute to meeting the targets of the Paris Agreement. Keynote speakers were Cristian Silviu Buşoi (ITRE Committee Chair), Hlne Chraye (Directorate Clean Planet of Directorate General Research & Innovation), Mark van Stiphout (Directorate General Energy), Bert Weckhuysen (SUNERGY coordinator), and Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens).

SUNERGY coordinator Bert Weckhuysen: The SUNERGY initiative comes at a time when greater attention to climate and energy issues and on-going developments at European level offer the right framework for action and a great opportunity to join efforts towards reversing climate change.

A common vision to close the carbon and nitrogen cycles

During the public kick-off meeting, the CSAs SUNRISE and ENERGY-X presented their achievements throughout the past year, and proposed their joint vision on providing sustainable and competitive alternatives to fossil fuels by 2050. Keynote speakers like Peter Drll (Director Prosperity, Directorate General Research & Innovation) highlighted the strong support of the European institutions towards R&I to achieve the ambitions of the European Green Deal.

SUNERGY deputy coordinator Frdric Chandezon: This kick-off meeting has served as a key step towards unifying the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X research communities and defining directions for large-scale initiatives within the new European R&I framework Horizon Europe.

Background

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X are two out of the six CSA projects that were selected for the Horizon 2020 call "FETFLAG-01-2018" within the research area of Energy, Environment and Climate Change. Both initiatives received 1 million from the European Commission to develop a detailed proposal for a large-scale research initiative during one year, from March 2019 to February 2020.

Both SUNRISE and ENERGY-X aim to develop sustainable approaches for the storage of renewable energy (solar and wind) through its conversion to fuels and commodity chemicals using abundant molecules such as carbon dioxide, water and nitrogen. The two projects bring together 30 committed organisations, backed by an initial supporting community of approx. 300 stakeholders from academia, industry, and society.

Media contacts:

SUNRISE Communication Team
contact@sunriseaction.eu
www.sunriseaction.eu

ENERGY-X Communication Team
contact@energy-x.eu
www.energy-x.eu

Annex 4: Briefing for politicians (next pages)

renewable fuel
and chemicals from
the air we breathe

WE WILL TRANSFORM

RAW MATERIALS THAT ARE ABUNDANTLY
AVAILABLE IN THE ATMOSPHERE

(water, carbon dioxide, nitrogen) into green fuels and chemicals. The process takes its energy directly from renewable sources, avoiding the drawbacks of current biofuels. It will increase the yield per hectare by at least ten times compared to biofuels, at half the price of fossil fuel.

THIS TECHNOLOGY

USES RENEWABLE ENERGY
TO REPLACE FOSSIL RESOURCES,

eliminates net CO₂ emissions, closes the carbon and nitrogen cycles locally and regionally, and feeds carbon into long-lasting materials.

THE GLOBAL ECOLOGICAL TRANSITION

THAT WE ENVISAGE WILL TAKE
AT LEAST 30 YEARS.

But 10 years will be enough to kickstart key technologies, and to turn the most advanced existing technologies into attractive commercial activities.

vision

2025

make fuel from CO₂ and
sunlight on a house roof

2030

run an airport and its flights,
entirely fossil-free

2050

use artificial photosynthesis and renewable
energy to produce carbon-neutral fuels
and chemicals across Europe

who we are

SUNERGY

Is a large community of scientists, engineers, world-leading multinational companies, innovative small and medium-sized enterprises, national and regional governments, civil society organisations and local authorities.

To date,
more than

300

companies
and organisations
have signed up to
our initiative.

Our supporters
come from

25

countries across
Europe and beyond,
including the United
States, Africa and
Australia.

SUNERGY

unites and builds on two
initiatives funded under

horizon 2020

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X.

They were selected by the European Commission to prepare for FET Flagship status, a billion-euro programme which identifies "visionary, science-driven, large-scale research initiatives addressing grand scientific and technological challenges".

our approach

SUNERGY

Is a game-changing, large-scale initiative to turn CO₂ and other atmospheric gases into fuels, fertilisers, plastics, pharmaceuticals and building materials with minimal land use. The process uses energy from renewable sources and can take advantage of existing infrastructure.

By closing the loop from a linear to a circular economy, Europe can decouple economic growth from resource consumption by 2050 – and become independent of fossil fuel imports which currently cost us hundreds of billions of euros every year.

Existing European partnerships focus on reducing the carbon footprint of 'downstream' activities, where products are produced and distributed.

By contrast, SUNERGY's pipeline of high-impact technologies will transform the supply side, harnessing renewable energy to convert CO₂ and other gases to fuels and chemicals at high efficiency.

This is a bold and ambitious response to the huge challenge of climate change. But we know that our linear economic model is unsustainable. So just fixing the existing system on the demand side is not enough.

1. SUNERGY will power the European Green Deal

By 2050, we will create carbon-neutral fuels and chemicals using abundant natural resources, decoupling Europe's reliance on rapidly-depleting fossil fuels.

Beyond that, they address three further priorities of the von der Leyen Commission:

2. SUNERGY will help build an economy that works for people

By 2050, we will produce sustainable fuels and chemicals that are affordable for everyone, creating millions of jobs and saving hundreds of billions of euros on imports of oil and natural gas.

3. SUNERGY will support the European way of life

By 2050, we will power an uncompromising high-energy-intensity society, where economic growth and prosperity are decoupled from the consumption of finite natural resources.

4. SUNERGY will promote a stronger Europe in the world

By 2050, we will decrease Europe's dependency on oil and gas imports with new global leadership in an arena of high-impact, game-changing technology.

milestones

2025

make fuel
from CO₂
and sunlight
on a house
roof

Plants use sunlight to convert ambient CO₂ into carbohydrates. By 2025, we will mimic this process in the laboratory at high efficiency, aiming for a much greater sunlight-to-CO₂ yield. This technology will allow European citizens to manufacture high-purity fuels and chemicals on demand, to any desired concentration, at an affordable cost, on their own house roof, farm or private garden.

2030

run an
airport and
its flights,
entirely
fossil-free

Around 30 million passengers travel through a mid-sized airport like Copenhagen each year, burning some 2 billion litres of aviation fuel. By 2030, we will completely replace the energy and fuel consumption of an airport like this, using electricity from renewable sources to power high-yield CO₂ conversion. This large-scale proof-of-concept will provide a blueprint for others to follow.

2050

**use artificial photosynthesis
and renewable energy to
produce carbon-neutral fuels
and chemicals across Europe**

Building on high-yield artificial photosynthesis and the efficient conversion of CO₂ and nitrogen with renewable energy, by 2050 we will provide access to scalable and affordable green fuels and chemicals across Europe. This will play a major role in eliminating the continent's unabated carbon emissions, displacing imported fossil fuels with a market potential of 250 billion euros per year and establishing Europe as the world's first carbon-neutral continent.

the science of SUNERGY: a work in progress

The scale of the challenge sets out to transform the EU's energy, transport and chemical industries. These industries are crucial to Europe's growth, competitiveness and quality of life - and their decarbonisation is a key element of the transition to a carbon-neutral Europe.

In 2017, the energy and transport sectors were jointly responsible for nearly 80% of Europe's greenhouse gas emissions, while the chemicals industry is entirely dependent on fossil-based raw materials and energy carriers. To make the clean energy transition a reality, growth must be decoupled from environmental pollution and the consumption of finite resources.

Over the last decade, much progress has been made in electricity production. New technologies and lower costs mean that wind and solar energy are now an established worldwide alternative to fossil fuels. But for transport and heating, fossil fuels are still an unmatched energy source with a huge existing infrastructure.

Battery technologies are part of the solution. But batteries alone cannot meet our needs, especially when it comes to air travel and long-distance haulage.

the answer: synthetic fuels and chemicals

To address these challenges, we need to create synthetic fuels and chemicals that allow us to store energy in chemical bonds. New forms of fuel will allow Europe to overcome seasonal variations in renewable electricity supply, and to transmit large quantities of energy over long distances. With the highest energy density of all energy storage media, synthetic fuels can store large amounts of energy cheaply over long periods of time. They also fit into our vast existing fuel infrastructure, originally built for the storage, transmission and use of fossil fuels.

The direct supply of energy-rich chemicals, from carbon feedstock for the chemical industry to nitrogen fertilizers for the supply of our food is an important step on the way to displacing fossil fuels by sustainable alternatives.

To address these challenges, we need to create synthetic fuels that allow us to store energy in chemical bonds. New forms of fuel will allow Europe to overcome seasonal variations in renewable electricity supply, and to transmit large quantities of energy over long distances. With the highest energy density of all energy storage media, synthetic fuels can store large amounts of energy cheaply over long periods of time. They also fit into our vast existing fuel infrastructure, originally built for the storage, transmission and use of fossil fuels.

At the same time, we will meet aspects of the European Green Deal towards decarbonising the chemical industry. Energy-rich synthetic chemicals will use air as a source of carbon and nitrogen, and the process of creating them will be powered by renewable energy, either using synthetic hydrogen fuels or from sustainable sources such as solar and wind power.

THE RIGHT AMOUNT OF ENERGY...

Different industries require different energy concentrations. Synthetic fuels can be manufactured to meet their exact needs.

...AT THE RIGHT TIME...

Synthetic fuels and chemicals allow energy to be stored and handled for use on different timescales: overnight, for a few days, for a season, or for many years.

...AT THE RIGHT LOCATION...

Decentralised manufacturing in a circular economy requires different forms of energy in smaller amounts at specific locations.

...IN THE RIGHT FORM...

Synthetic fuels convert and store energy to the exact form in which it will be used, avoiding complex and inefficient multi-step conversions.

...AT THE BEST EFFICIENCY AND HIGHEST YIELD...

High efficiency is key. For artificial photosynthesis using sunlight, we target photon-to-product yields of at least 70%.

...WITH EFFICIENT MATERIALS ON DEMAND...

Synthetic fuels use materials efficiently and therefore minimise the costs of extraction, storage and transport, especially when it comes to materials that are rare in the earth's crust.

...AND AT THE BEST PRICE!

The latest developments in artificial photosynthesis will allow us to reach 70% photon-to-product yields. At this level, less than 3% of the surface of Europe could provide all fuels and chemicals we need - less than half of the area currently devoted to housing, transport and commerce - vastly reducing conversion and distribution costs.

where next?

to make **SUNERGY** a reality Europe needs:

strong political and scientific/ technological leadership:

to coordinate a complex undertaking across many borders and among many partners.

a sophisticated organisational framework:

to successfully bring together many different sectors, disciplines, levels of governance, levels of technology maturity, funding schemes and national interests.

a clear long-term strategy:

to take on and overcome technological and societal challenges.

multiple, semi-independent, parallel development routes:

to provide additional assurance of success given the early stage of development of some technologies.

substantial public finance:

to de-risk investment,
kickstart the most
promising technologies and
allow rapid scaling-up.

commitment from private investors:

to ensure buy-in and match
public funding with the
support of major
international players

European partnerships - as they exist already today and in their future shape under Horizon Europe - are designed specifically to enable large-scale, transformative projects such as these. Indeed, several partnerships currently being discussed by the European Commission and member states address themes that are also central to **SUNERGY**. This is proof of the relevance the European decision-makers and industry assign to them. However, these current partnerships focus on downstream conversion technology. A partnership that unlocks the benefits of upstream technologies, settled in existing urban zones by developing existing infrastructure, is an indispensable complement to these.

unlocking the renewable energy future

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ENERGY-X

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Be a change maker & Join our community!

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SUNRISE – Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

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